

Individual or Group Error Compensation: An Experimental Demonstration on the Frequency Response of Rogowski Coils

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Abstract—Instrument transformers (ITs) play a crucial role as interface elements in power systems, enabling the acquisition of electrical quantities necessary for assessing system health. Consequently, they have been a focal point in research, with numerous studies aiming to enhance their performance in field applications. One critical issue affecting the accuracy of ITs is the differentiation between type and routine tests, which underscores the need for individual or group error compensation. This study investigates the limitations of group error compensation techniques for ITs, providing experimental evidence to demonstrate their potential drawbacks. Specifically, low-power current transformers, such as Rogowski coils, were evaluated to examine variability among individual devices. The study tested three series of six devices from three manufacturers under varying temperature conditions. The findings reveal significant variability among the tested devices, indicating that group error compensation often degrades the accuracy of ITs. These results highlight the importance of considering individual error characteristics to ensure optimal performance in practical applications.

Keywords—Rogowski coils, error compensation, temperature, sensors, accuracy, measurement, testing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Monitoring the power system is essential for ensuring its reliability, efficiency, and stability. It allows operators to detect anomalies, predict failures, and implement timely corrective actions, thereby minimizing outages and maintaining the quality of power delivery. In an era of increasing integration of renewable energy sources, electric vehicles, and other decentralized loads, the complexity of power systems has grown significantly [1]. Continuous monitoring helps manage this complexity by providing real-time insights into system performance, ensuring compliance with regulatory standards, and enhancing overall system resilience. Effective monitoring also enables predictive maintenance, reducing downtime and operational costs, while improving safety and extending the lifespan of critical infrastructure. Instrument transformers (ITs) are indispensable tools for power system monitoring due to their ability to accurately measure electrical quantities such as voltage, current, and then compute power under a wide range of conditions. They provide the scaled-down signals necessary for control, protection, and measurement equipment, ensuring safety by electrically isolating high-voltage circuits from low-voltage instruments. ITs offer high accuracy and are designed

to operate reliably in harsh environmental conditions, making them ideal for long-term monitoring. Their ability to function seamlessly in both steady-state and transient conditions allows for accurate data acquisition, which is critical for analyzing system performance and diagnosing issues [2,3]. This makes ITs a cornerstone of modern power system monitoring and management strategies. However, ITs are subject to inherent errors due to manufacturing tolerances, environmental conditions, and operational stresses. Error compensation techniques, whether applied individually or to groups of ITs, aim to mitigate these inaccuracies, ensuring compliance with stringent performance standards. Individual error compensation involves calibrating each ITs to account for its unique error profile, offering the highest precision and performance but often at a higher cost and complexity. On the other hand, group error compensation relies on averaged error characteristics across a batch of devices, providing a more economical approach but potentially sacrificing accuracy, especially when significant variability exists among devices. The choice of compensation technique depends on the application, with individual compensation being preferred for critical measurements and group compensation suitable for less sensitive tasks. In this perspective, literature provide many solutions. For example, [4] introduced a Current Transformer Error Compensation Unit that uses manufacturer-provided error data to apply correction coefficients, effectively improving measurement accuracy under diverse conditions. In [5] authors proposed a novel method to mitigate harmonic distortion in voltage transformers, particularly at low-order harmonics, achieving improved accuracy through a compensation approach validated via simulations. As for [6] deep learning, specifically an autoencoder, was leveraged to address current transformer saturation by reconstructing undistorted waveforms, demonstrating strong performance under varied scenarios. Finally, [7] developed an FPGA-based adaptive phase-shift compensation method for electronic instrument transformers, dynamically calibrating phase errors in real-time to ensure high precision, with experimental results supporting its validity.

The purpose of this work is not to assess these promising techniques but to emphasize the importance of clarity in determining when to apply group or individual error compensation. To validate the authors' hypothesis experimentally, three groups of six identical Rogowski coils (RCs), sourced from three different manufacturers, were

tested simultaneously. Accuracy measurements were conducted under varying temperature conditions, as temperature significantly influences the performance of Rogowski coils. The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section II introduces the scenario to the reader, focusing on the motivation and on the role of influence quantities. The core is presented in Section III, in which the measurement setup and the tests are described. All the results are listed and commented on in Section IV. Finally, a conclusion is drawn in Section V.

II. SCENARIO

A. Influence quantities

Rogowski coils are widely utilized in power systems for measuring AC currents and, with certain adjustments, can also measure DC currents. These sensors are known for having several advantages: (i) their ability to handle large currents without saturation or significant heat production making them ideal for demanding applications; (ii) their non-intrusivity and flexibility thank to their design that allow them to open and consequently there is no direct contact when they are installed around the conductor, which helps to reduce the risk of damage or interruptions to the system; (iii) their wide linear frequency response up to tens of kHz; (iv) being lightweight due to the absence of iron core; and finally (v) no danger and damages from open-circuited secondaries and large overloads [8]. Despite their advantages, RCs come with certain challenges. Their installation and calibration demand technical expertise, which can be a barrier for some users, since the output of the RC is highly dependent on the position of the conductor contained by the transducer itself. Furthermore, they are sensitive to external factors and the most influential are: (i) the magnetic fields (usually induced by from currents flowing in adjacent phases in three-phase systems), which can lead to inaccuracies if proper shielding is not implemented [9] and (ii) the ambient temperature [10]. Finally, they need an integration stage for the output voltage being proportional to the derivative of the current. Nevertheless, the combination of their flexibility, accuracy, and non-intrusive design makes RCs a preferred solution for various power system applications.

Such factors are known as influence quantities (IQs), defined as “quantity which is not the subject of the measurement and whose change affects the relationship between the indication and the result of the measurement” [11]. The effect of the IQs on the accuracy of a device could be so significant that results might be totally compromised. Other examples of IQs that affect ITs are humidity [12], altitude, pressure, and vibration [14].

B. Standards

The IEC 61869-10 standard [15] is specifically dedicated to low-power current transformers (LPCTs) with particular focus on RCs used for measurement applications. It establishes requirements and guidelines on various aspects and among the most important there are: (i) design and manufacturing, (ii) testing (with particular attention to those on the position and influence of adjacent phases), (iii) accuracy, (iv) operating condition, (v) ratings.

Furthermore, the new version of IEC 61869-1 [16] states general requirements for ITs and low-power instrument transformers (LPITs) that can also be applicable to RCs.

Both standards report a list of tests which are classified according to: type, routine, special, commissioning and

sample test. Basic accuracy tests, to prove compliance with the specified accuracy class in measuring the fundamental, are type tests. Furthermore, these standards suggest additional quantities with respect to which to analyze accuracy of the device under test and, among these, temperature is a variable of interest. Finally, to ensure the long-term consistency of the manufacturing process quality, it is recommended to perform only the lightning impulse test on the primary terminals as the sample test. These standards play a critical role in ensuring consistency and reliability in their use across various power systems, enabling precise current measurement and effective system monitoring. Adhering to these standards is essential to ensure the accuracy and interoperability of RCs in power system applications.

C. Motivation

Building on the previous subsection, the motivation and contribution of this paper lie in experimentally validating the theory that distinguishing between group and individual error compensation is not always straightforward. This challenge adds to the numerous difficulties already encountered when performing in-field measurements, where conditions deviate significantly from the controlled environment of a laboratory. Furthermore, this work paves the way for future investigations, encouraging the scientific community to explore related questions and further refine measurement techniques.

III. USE CASE

This section presents the measurement setup and the testing approach in two dedicated paragraphs.

A. Measurement setup

The measurement setup adopted in this paper is depicted in Fig. 1. It consists of: (i) a Fluke calibrator 6105A which controls a Fluke transconductance 52120A, both in metrological confirmation; (ii) a reference shunt resistor of value equal to 1 m Ω with a maximum uncertainty of $2 \cdot 10^{-6}$ Ω ; (iii) a data acquisition system consisting of a chassis containing two National Instruments data acquisition board NI-9238, each with the following main features: (a) 4 input channels, (b) 24 bits, (c) full scale of ± 0.5 mV, (d) maximum sampling frequency of 50 kS/s/ch; (iv) a climatic chamber. Finally, the configuration includes six nominally identical commercial (same type and same manufacturer) RUTs (Rogowski under test) placed together inside the climatic chamber. Table I summarizes the main characteristics of the three different types. In a nutshell, the measurement setup works in the following way: the transconductance, controlled by the calibrator, generates a current $i_p(t)$ at 50 Hz having a certain amplitude according to Table II. Then, this current flows into the six RUTs contained in the climatic chamber at a certain temperature according to Fig. 2. Finally, the output of the RUTs and the reference shunt are collected by the data acquisition system controlled in LabVIEW environment.

TABLE I. MAIN FEATURES OF THE RUTS

	RUT α	RUT β	RUT γ
Accuracy	± 0.5 %	± 1 %	± 1 %
Ratio [mV/kA]	50	100	100
Rated current [kA]	0.1	1	1
Technology	Split-core	Split-core	Split-core

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the measurement setup.

B. Description of the tests

The approach involves measuring the outputs of six identical RUTs (Rogowski Under Test) subject to the same current and temperature conditions. Three types of Rogowski coils (RCs), sourced from different manufacturers (α , β , and γ), were selected, with six identical sensors tested for each type. During the design of the setup, particular care was taken to ensure the conductor carrying the test current was centered relative to each RUT and that all RUTs were equidistant from the conductor. This minimized external influences and ensured uniform test conditions, isolating the effects of temperature and current. The test signals were generated using a transconductance device, producing a desired sinusoidal current at 50 Hz with amplitudes increasing as specified in Table II. For each test signal, the data acquisition system captured and stored 100 frequency response measurements from both the reference shunt and the RUTs. Each acquisition lasted 1 second, ensuring comprehensive data collection for analysis.

As for the test temperatures, the selected values for testing, as referenced in [15], are -5 °C, 20 °C, and 40 °C. The standard specifies that, beyond room temperature, testing must include the minimum and maximum operating ambient temperatures defined by the RCs temperature class. Additionally, manufacturers are required to provide thermal constant for their devices in order to know how long it takes to reach thermal stability. However, none of the tested devices included this information (like many other manufacturers). To address this gap, preliminary tests were conducted to estimate the thermal constant of the RUTs. These tests revealed that a stabilization period of 3 hours is sufficient to achieve thermal equilibrium.

Based on these findings, Fig. 2 shows the shape of the cycle reproduced by the climatic chamber. The rate of temperature change between any two points in the cycle is set at 0.1 °C/min. In conclusion, the measurements are carried out in three time-windows for each type of RUTs.

TABLE II. MAIN FEATURES OF THE TEST SIGNALS

Frequency [Hz]	Amplitude [A]
50	9
	25
	50
	75
	90

Fig. 2. Temperature cycle accuracy test.

IV. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

A. Experimental Results

To assess the experimental results, the ratio error ε and phase displacement $\Delta\varphi$ are calculated according to the following equations:

$$\varepsilon(\%) = \frac{K_r U_s - U_p}{U_p} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta\varphi = \varphi_s - \varphi_p \quad (2)$$

The two formulas include the following parameters: (i) the rated transformation ratio K_r of the RUTs under test, (ii) the rms fundamental component of the primary and secondary, U_p and U_s , respectively, (iii) the phase of the primary and secondary, φ_p and φ_s , respectively.

For the sake of clarity, the results are reported according to the following nomenclature. The letters α , β , and γ refer to a different typology of RUTs, as indicated in Table I. While the numbers 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6, used in the tables reporting the results, refer to the six Rogowski coils of the same manufacturer tested together.

For each RUTs, all the obtained results are presented: (i) in Table III, IV and V for α -type RC, (ii) in Table VI, VII and VIII for β -type RC and finally in Table IX, X and XI for γ -type RC.

TABLE III. RATIO ERROR AND PHASE DISPLACEMENT FOR EACH α -TYPE RUT AT 20 °C

Ratio Error [%] at 20 °C					
α -type RC	Amplitude [A]				
	9	25	50	75	90
1	0.368	0.362	0.369	0.376	0.375
2	0.089	0.093	0.102	0.109	0.107
3	-0.086	-0.088	-0.081	-0.074	-0.076
4	0.289	0.289	0.296	0.303	0.301
5	-0.054	-0.056	-0.049	-0.042	-0.045
6	0.176	0.177	0.185	0.193	0.192
Phase displacement [mrad] at 20 °C					
α -type RC	Amplitude [A]				
	9	25	50	75	90
1	-0.46	-0.44	-0.45	-0.46	-0.46
2	-0.45	-0.47	-0.48	-0.48	-0.47
3	-0.46	-0.45	-0.46	-0.46	-0.45
4	-0.44	-0.46	-0.47	-0.47	-0.47
5	-0.45	-0.45	-0.46	-0.46	-0.46
6	-0.48	-0.48	-0.49	-0.50	-0.49

TABLE IV. RATIO ERROR AND PHASE DISPLACEMENT FOR EACH α -TYPE RUT AT 40 °C

Ratio Error [%] at 40 °C					
α -type RC	Amplitude [A]				
	9	25	50	75	90
1	0.114	0.111	0.119	0.107	0.098
2	-0.179	-0.178	-0.170	-0.182	-0.191
3	-0.366	-0.369	-0.362	-0.374	-0.383
4	0.039	0.036	0.044	0.032	0.022
5	-0.315	-0.320	-0.314	-0.326	-0.336
6	-0.090	-0.091	-0.083	-0.094	-0.102
Phase displacement [mrad] at 40 °C					
α -type RC	Amplitude [A]				
	9	25	50	75	90
1	-0.44	-0.42	-0.43	-0.44	-0.44
2	-0.48	-0.47	-0.47	-0.47	-0.47
3	-0.46	-0.44	-0.44	-0.45	-0.45
4	-0.46	-0.45	-0.45	-0.46	-0.46
5	-0.49	-0.45	-0.45	-0.45	-0.45
6	-0.49	-0.48	-0.48	-0.49	-0.49

TABLE V. RATIO ERROR AND PHASE DISPLACEMENT FOR EACH α -TYPE RUT AT -5 °C

Ratio Error [%] at -5 °C					
α -type RC	Amplitude [A]				
	9	25	50	75	90
1	1.289	1.280	1.284	1.277	1.270
2	0.961	0.960	0.965	0.959	0.951
3	0.849	0.845	0.850	0.844	0.838
4	1.157	1.152	1.157	1.151	1.144
5	0.907	0.899	0.901	0.896	0.888
6	1.086	1.083	1.086	1.081	1.074
Phase displacement [mrad] at -5 °C					
α -type RC	Amplitude [A]				
	9	25	50	75	90
1	-0.41	-0.40	-0.40	-0.42	-0.42
2	-0.44	-0.44	-0.44	-0.45	-0.45
3	-0.41	-0.41	-0.42	-0.43	-0.43
4	-0.42	-0.43	-0.43	-0.44	-0.44
5	-0.42	-0.42	-0.43	-0.44	-0.43
6	-0.43	-0.45	-0.46	-0.47	-0.47

Beginning with a general observation, all tables present results with a number of digits that accurately represent the associated standard deviation.

As a first consideration on α -type RC, it is clearly noted that: (i) the variability of the ratio error values is significantly more pronounced than that of the phase displacement values; (ii) the variability between identical sensors subjected to the same temperature and current values is greater than the variability observed for the same sensor under increasing current values thank to the linearity offered by RCs. Therefore, the focus of the analysis can be narrowed to the ratio error index, and this is why the phase displacement is not provided anymore in Tables VI to XI. Another comment on the ratio error in Table III is that, as expected, the accuracy of all devices falls within the accuracy limit of their classes but are far from being similar. These experimental results support the hypothesis that, even at 20 °C, group error compensation is not suitable or beneficial.

By looking at the results for β -type and γ -type RCs, the same conclusion can be drawn. In fact, both exhibit good linearity in the current amplitude range and the 6 RCs in each type behave quite similarly.

TABLE VI. RATIO ERROR FOR EACH β -TYPE RUT AT 20 °C

Ratio Error [%] at 20 °C					
β -type RC	Amplitude [A]				
	9	25	50	75	90
1	-0.314	-0.316	-0.305	-0.292	-0.313
2	-0.272	-0.274	-0.263	-0.250	-0.271
3	-0.371	-0.371	-0.359	-0.345	-0.366
4	-0.177	-0.177	-0.166	-0.152	-0.173
5	-0.221	-0.220	-0.205	-0.189	-0.210
6	-0.248	-0.244	-0.227	-0.210	-0.230

TABLE VII. RATIO ERROR FOR EACH β -TYPE RUT AT 40 °C

Ratio Error [%] at 40 °C					
β -type RC	Amplitude [A]				
	9	25	50	75	90
1	-1.285	-1.284	-1.280	-1.274	-1.294
2	-1.241	-1.244	-1.239	-1.232	-1.254
3	-1.303	-1.305	-1.299	-1.291	-1.313
4	-1.140	-1.139	-1.135	-1.128	-1.149
5	-1.170	-1.171	-1.163	-1.153	-1.174
6	-1.211	-1.209	-1.199	-1.188	-1.208

TABLE VIII. RATIO ERROR FOR EACH β -TYPE RUTS AT -5 °C

Ratio Error [%] at -5 °C					
β -type RC	Amplitude [A]				
	9	25	50	75	90
1	0.856	0.854	0.860	0.861	0.841
2	0.888	0.887	0.893	0.895	0.874
3	0.814	0.815	0.821	0.823	0.804
4	0.991	0.993	0.999	1.001	0.981
5	0.953	0.955	0.965	0.969	0.950
6	0.930	0.935	0.947	0.952	0.933

TABLE IX. RATIO ERROR FOR EACH γ -TYPE RUTS AT 20 °C

Ratio Error [%] at 20 °C					
γ -type RC	Amplitude [A]				
	9	25	50	75	90
1	-2.140	-2.150	-2.147	-2.146	-2.183
2	-2.102	-2.103	-2.098	-2.096	-2.132
3	-2.062	-2.070	-2.075	-2.079	-2.117
4	-2.109	-2.108	-2.091	-2.082	-2.116
5	-0.901	-0.911	-0.906	-0.906	-0.943
6	-1.981	-1.988	-1.979	-1.975	-2.011

TABLE X. RATIO ERROR FOR EACH γ -TYPE RUTS AT 40 °C

Ratio Error [%] at 40 °C					
γ -type RC	Amplitude [A]				
	9	25	50	75	90
1	-1.916	-1.920	-1.907	-1.863	-1.802
2	-1.835	-1.836	-1.818	-1.772	-1.709
3	-1.803	-1.811	-1.800	-1.760	-1.701
4	-1.839	-1.834	-1.809	-1.757	-1.690
5	-0.637	-0.642	-0.627	-0.583	-0.520
6	-1.211	-1.209	-1.199	-1.188	-1.208

TABLE XI. RATIO ERROR FOR EACH γ -TYPE RUTS AT -5 °C

Ratio Error [%] at -5 °C					
γ -type RC	Amplitude [A]				
	9	25	50	75	90
1	-1.639	-1.638	-1.637	-1.624	-1.600
2	-1.602	-1.593	-1.595	-1.573	-1.548
3	-1.577	-1.582	-1.589	-1.576	-1.555

4	-1.642	-1.638	-1.615	-1.601	-1.572
5	-0.376	-0.380	-0.372	-0.363	-0.338
6	-1.474	-1.476	-1.460	-1.451	-1.425

Fig. 3. Ratio error for each RUTs of α -type for test current of 90 A

Fig. 4. $\Delta\varepsilon$ (%) for each RUTs of α -type for test current of 90 A

Fig. 5. $\Delta\varepsilon$ (%) for each RUTs of β -type for test current of 90 A

An interesting aspect regarding the behaviour of the ratio error is given for the α -type RC (but it applies to all), in Fig. 3. It depicts, in the case of a measured current of 90 A how different the results are among the 6 devices. Variations from a minimum of 50 % to a maximum of 600 % (at 20 °C) are observed. This clearly demonstrates the potential inefficacy of group error compensation techniques.

Another consideration, the γ -type of RUTs has accuracy class 1, but presents a ratio error that often exceeds 2%. However, these values are reasonable since the nominal current is equal to 1 kA and in addition they respect the limits indicated in Table 1001 of the standard [4], which, for a class 1 sensor, provides a limit for the ratio error of 3 % in the case of a test current equal to 5 % of the nominal primary current

Fig. 6. $\Delta\varepsilon$ (%) for each RUTs of γ -type for test current of 90 A

or of 1.5 % in the case of a test current equal to 20 % of the nominal primary current.

One final comment on the 3 set of results of the RC types is on the variation of the ratio error over temperature. This aspect is not specifically analyzed because it is well-known in literature and already addressed by authors in [10]. Therefore, the focus is kept on the novelty of the paper.

To further validate the authors' initial hypothesis, the obtained results are evaluated through the formula:

$$\Delta\varepsilon(\%) = |\varepsilon_{T_1} - \varepsilon_{T_2}| \quad (3)$$

which includes ε_{T_1} and ε_{T_2} , the ratio errors calculated at temperatures T_1 and T_2 . This expression allows for an immediate evaluation of the different behavior of the 6 RC inside each type in terms of ratio error. The results of the implementation of (3) are displayed in Fig. 4, 5, and 6, for RC type α , β , and γ , respectively. In Fig. 4, transitioning from one temperature to other results in a percentage variation for re ratio error of approximately 9 % for similar α -type RUTs. This variation is non-negligible and should be considered when applying compensation techniques. In contrast, in Fig. 5, β -type RUTs show a percentage variation between temperature increments of approximately 2%, smaller than in the previous case, but still a further contribution to uncertainty that would lead to incorrect compensation if performed on the entire sensor group instead of addressing each sensor individually.

As regards the variability of the ratio error for the γ -type RUTs, these devices demonstrate a percentage variation decidedly more marked that varies from a minimum value of 11% up to 110%, as can be estimated from Fig. 6. In conclusion, the hypothesis advanced by the authors is confirmed by all three types of RUTs tested, in particular two (α and γ) show a significant percentage variation in the ratio error when moving from one temperature to another.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper investigates the magnitude of the error that may be introduced when group compensation techniques are applied to a set of identical Rogowski coils. The results were validated by means of three types of RCs produced by different manufacturers and, for each type, six commercially RCs were tested together under identical thermal conditions at three distinct temperatures defined by the standards. The experimental results confirm that similar devices exhibit different ratio errors when subjected to the same temperature—a known phenomenon. However, the study further validates the authors' hypothesis: when transitioning between temperatures, the percentage variation in ratio error differs among devices, even within the same group. If this variability is not accounted for, group compensation

techniques may result in incorrect adjustments, which could be avoided through device-specific compensation. The research aims to shed light on the uncertainty introduced by group compensation methods and to provide deeper insights into the trade-offs between group and individual compensation approaches. Group compensation is less precise but more cost-effective, whereas individual compensation offers greater accuracy at a higher cost. This study seeks to support informed decision-making when selecting the most appropriate compensation technique.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The project 22NRM06 ADMIT has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and from by the Participating State.

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